

Computations behind the *Weighted Code Evolution Significance*

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1 Preconditions

The user can select through the input fields the *Weights of Significance* of Reliability (bugs), Security (security hotspots), Maintainability (code smells), Test Coverage and Duplicated-Lines represented by $w_{bugs} > 0$, $w_{secu} > 0$, $w_{code} > 0$, $w_{test} > 0$ and $w_{dupl} > 0$. In addition the following equation must be fulfilled:

$$w_{bugs} + w_{secu} + w_{code} + w_{test} + w_{dupl} = 1$$

2 Computation

2.1 *SonarQube* Measurements

By performing a code analysis (using SonarQube) for each run on a specific date, a value is generated that corresponds to a particular aspect of software quality. For the following we assume:

1. In total, n analysis were executed.
2. All values are represented by tuples x^{bugs} , x^{secu} , x^{code} , x^{test} and x^{dupl} , sorted by time.
3. We use the notations $a \in \{bugs, secu, code, test, dupl\}$ and $l \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ to represent the measurement result x_l^a of the software quality aspect a for the l^{th} analysis.

2.2 Change between to Successive Analysis

As a first step, the change between two successive analysis x_{m-1}^a and x_m^a for the specific software quality aspect a is represented through the following equation:

$$y_m^a = |x_{m+1}^a - x_m^a| \geq 0$$

In this way, we receive new tuples

- $y^{bugs} = (y_0^{bugs}, y_1^{bugs}, \dots, y_{n-1}^{bugs})$
- $y^{secu} = (y_0^{secu}, y_1^{secu}, \dots, y_{n-1}^{secu})$
- $y^{code} = (y_0^{code}, y_1^{code}, \dots, y_{n-1}^{code})$
- $y^{test} = (y_0^{test}, y_1^{test}, \dots, y_{n-1}^{test})$
- $y^{dupl} = (y_0^{dupl}, y_1^{dupl}, \dots, y_{n-1}^{dupl})$

2.3 Sorting

The elements of the tuples y^{bugs} , y^{secu} , y^{code} , y^{test} and y^{dupl} are then **sorted by the size** and **duplicates** are removed. The respective tuples are labeled with z^{bugs} , z^{secu} , z^{code} , z^{test} and z^{dupl} .

2.4 Mapping of *Specific Significance Value*

Based on the previous step, we will map each y_a^m to a *Specific Significance Value*, that represents the significance of this change compared to all other changes of the specific code quality metric a . This is done in the following way: The **position of y_a^m in the tuple z^a** represents the *Specific Significance Value* and is label with s_a^m .

2.5 Calculation of *Weighted Code Evolution Significance*

The following equations represent the *Weighted Code Evolution Significance* s_m of all quality aspects for a specific change m :

$$\begin{aligned} s_m = & w_{bugs} * \frac{s_{bugs}^m}{\#(z^{bugs})} + \\ & w_{secu} * \frac{s_{secu}^m}{\#(z^{secu})} + \\ & w_{code} * \frac{s_{code}^m}{\#(z^{code})} + \\ & w_{test} * \frac{s_{test}^m}{\#(z^{test})} + \\ & w_{dupl} * \frac{s_{dupl}^m}{\#(z^{dupl})} \end{aligned}$$

with $\#(z^a)$ size of tuple z^a .